

GALL BLADDER WALL EDEMA- CHOLECYSTECTOMY NOT FOR ALL

Parveen Malhotra, Rahul Siwach, Bibin CF, Chitrakshi Bhardwaj,

Avani Sharma, Abhishek Yadav

Department of Medical Gastroenterology, PGIMS, Rohtak, Haryana, India

*Corresponding author: Parveen Malhotra, Department of Medical Gastroenterology, PGIMS, Rohtak & 128/19, Civil Hospital Road, Rohtak, Haryana, India

Abstract

Introduction: Gallbladder (GB) wall edema is a common, often non-surgical, finding characterized by fluid accumulation and thickening of the gallbladder wall (>3 mm) on imaging. While associated with acute cholecystitis, it is frequently caused by non-primary diseases like congestive heart failure, hepatitis, renal failure, or hypoalbuminemia. It is generally a transient, secondary condition, often resolving when the underlying illness is treated.

Case Series: Our department is model treatment centre for free treatment of hepatitis B & C under National viral hepatitis control program (NVHCP). It is high flow center where on daily basis 70-80 patients of hepatitis B and C come for consultation. Out of them 15-20 are new and rest 55-60 are old patients. We frequently see many acute hepatitis B patients and till date, 700 acute hepatitis B patients and 100 acute HCV patients have been enrolled. In addition, till date 300 patients of acute hepatitis A & E have been enrolled. In addition, our department of medical gastroenterology commonly encounter alcoholic hepatitis, dengue, malarial, enteric and autoimmune hepatitis patients. Approximately, more than 2000 patients in total of acute hepatitis, including all aetiology have been seen and followed up clinically. In half of them (around) 1000 patients, they had gall bladder wall edema but none was advised for cholecystectomy and every body recovered once baseline aetiological factor of hepatitis was resolved. All of them were symptomatically treated with ursodeoxycholic acid, proton pump inhibitors, prokinetics, anti-allergic, multivitamin and antiviral therapy where indicated. In last fifteen years, we encountered five patients of acute hepatitis with gall bladder wall edema who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy at private hospitals, thinking it to be acalculous cholecystitis. Normally, in acute viral hepatitis, the serum transaminases (AST & ALT) are raised to ten times i.e. more than 400 IU/ml and serum bilirubin level are also significantly raised but in cholecystitis, the increase in transaminases and serum bilirubin level is lesser than acute viral hepatitis. Moreover, pain abdomen in acute viral hepatitis is usually dull ache due to stretching of liver capsule which is in contrast of pain of acute cholecystitis which is very severe and radiating to right shoulder. The fever in acute cholecystitis is persistent in comparison to acute viral hepatitis in which it occurs only in initial phase. In cases of alcoholic hepatitis, dengue, malarial, enteric and autoimmune hepatitis patients, they all can be separated on basis of clinical history and other supportive biochemical and serological investigations which are specific to particular disease.

Conclusion: Any patient with gall bladder edema, especially in absence of cholelithiasis should be evaluated for causes unrelated to gall bladder like hepatitis, so as to avoid unwarranted cholecystectomies and decrease associated morbidity and mortality. In our large study pool of 1000 patients of acute hepatitis were saved from unwarranted laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Keywords: Gall bladder wall edema, Ultrasonogram, Computed tomography scan, Endoscopic ultrasonogram, Cholecystectomy

Introduction-

Gall bladder wall edema is generally categorized by whether the primary issue is inside or outside the gallbladder. The primary or intrinsic causes include acute calculous cholecystitis, acalculous cholecystitis, chronic cholecystitis or carcinoma gall bladder. The secondary (extrinsic) causes include hepatic causes (acute hepatitis, cirrhosis portal hypertension), congestive heart failure (due to elevated systemic venous pressure), renal failure (due to fluid retention and hypoalbuminemia) and systemic infections like Dengue or malaria. [1] In secondary or edematous wall thickening of the gallbladder is often accompanied by a periportal collar sign, which likely represents periportal edema. [2] The gallbladder wall comprises three layers: mucosa, muscularis, and serosa. On ultrasound (US) the innermost mucosa layer is hyperechoic, the middle muscularis layer is a hypo-echoic (constituting mainly smooth muscle), and the serosa is a thin smooth membrane covering the gallbladder. [3] A thickened gallbladder wall presents on US as a “double-rim” where both the inner (mucosa) and outermost (serosa) layers are hyperechoic, and the middle (muscularis) layer is hypoechoic. In patients with hepatitis, US and non-contrast CT display pericholecystic fluid and edema. In acute hepatitis the liver may have the characteristic “starry sky” appearance characterized by a hypoechoic liver with prominent portal triads. [4]

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severe and radiating to right shoulder. The fever in acute cholecystitis is persistent in comparison to acute viral hepatitis in which it occurs only in initial phase. In cases of alcoholic hepatitis, dengue, malarial, enteric and autoimmune hepatitis patients, they all can be separated on basis of clinical history and other supportive biochemical and serological investigations which are specific to particular disease.

Figure 1- Ultrasonogram abdomen showing gall bladder wall edema in Acute Viral Hepatitis (White arrows)

Discussion –

Gallbladder wall edema is a common extrahepatic finding in acute viral hepatitis, seen in over 50% of cases, particularly hepatitis A. It appears on ultrasound as diffuse wall thickening (>3 mm) and a "double-wall" sign and is caused by hypoalbuminemia or direct inflammation; it is often managed conservatively. This finding can mimic acute acalculous cholecystitis, making it critical to distinguish from true surgical cholecystitis, as unnecessary surgery should be avoided in acute hepatitis patients. The edema arises from a combination of factors, including reduced albumin levels (hypoalbuminemia), increased portal pressure, and local spread of inflammation from the diseased liver. The thickening is usually temporary and resolves spontaneously with the improvement of the viral hepatitis. Gallbladder wall edema is associated with elevated liver enzymes (ALT/AST), often correlating with the severity of the hepatic inflammation. In viral diseases such as hepatitis, viral infiltrations, as well as direct cellular liver damage, are the cause of gallbladder edema. Hepatitis A, a common cause of acute viral disease, causes acute liver failure in 0.5% as well as thickening of the gallbladder wall as an extrahepatic involvement. In other viral diseases like dengue, it has been reported that in the early stages, capillary plasma leakage occurs, leading to thickening of the gallbladder wall in up to a third of them. [5]

Conclusion-

Any patient with gall bladder edema, especially in absence of cholelithiasis should be evaluated for causes unrelated to gall bladder like hepatitis, so as to avoid unwarranted cholecystectomies and decrease associated morbidity and mortality. In our large study pool of 1000 patients of acute hepatitis were saved from unwarranted laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Conflict of Interest –

The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest and no funding was taken from any source to conduct this research. The consent was taken from the patient and family members before publication of this paper.

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